

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 22

• China

More Raphidophyte Blooms in South China Waters

There have been two Raphidophyceae blooms, as well as a number of other blooms recorded in Dapeng Bay in the early part of this year. A *Heterosigma akashiwo* bloom occurred in the inner bayments of Dapeng Bay. In April 2001, a mixed bloom of *Chattonella ovata* and *Chattonella globosa* was recorded in the same area.

The first Raphidophyceae bloom, *Heterosigma* sp., was recorded in South China waters in the late 1980s. No other Raphidophyceae bloom was recorded until 1993, when a *Chattonella marina* bloom occurred in Dapeng Bay. Since then, more and more Raphidophyceae species, e.g. *Chattonella antiqua*, *C. globosa*, and *C. ovata* have been found in these waters.

South China waters are one of the locations with the most frequent HAB occurrences in the world. In recent years, more and more new harmful species have been recorded in these waters. An historical bloom, which caused major fish kills in the South China waters affected by the bloom, was due to a newly identified species,

Figure 1. *Chattonella ovata* and *Chattonella globosa*

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• Mediterranean Sea

Spreading of *Gymnodinium catenatum* Graham in the western Mediterranean Sea

Gymnodinium catenatum Graham is a naked, chain-forming dinoflagellate causing Paralytic Shellfish Poison (PSP) events in several parts of the world [1]. In Europe, *G. catenatum* was described for the first time in the Galician rias (NW Spain) in 1976 after a PSP event [2], hypothetically introduced by fishing ships from Argentina [3]. Another possibility for the origin is the historic presence of the species in inshore Moroccan Atlantic waters [3] where PSP events have been recorded since the 1970s, but *G. catenatum* was not identified there

until 1982 [4,5]. It has also appeared along the coasts of Portugal and Gulf of Cadiz [6,7] and for first time in the Mediterranean Sea along the NW Alboran coast [8,9]. Recently *G. catenatum* has been reported in Eastern Mediterranean waters near the Suez Canal [10].

There are erroneous descriptions of the geographical expansion of *G. catenatum* due to confusion with two non-toxic species [11,12,13]. Along the European Atlantic coasts these records corresponded to *Gymnodinium nolleri* Ellegaard et Moestrup

[14,15] and in the Mediterranean Sea correspond to *Gyrodinium impudicum* Fraga et Bravo [16,17,18].

From Lugol fixed samples, the primary evidence for the differentiation between *Gyrodinium impudicum* and *G. catenatum* is colony size. *G. catenatum* can form colonies of up to 64 individuals whereas the colony size of *G. impudicum* comprises generally 4 or rarely 8 individuals [19,13]. Before the description of *G. impudicum*, the presence of short colonies was attributed

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Karenia digitata [1]. A number of other species new to these waters have also been recorded [2].

Why are there more and more new harmful species or new records found in South China waters? One answer is definitely that there have been both more and intensive monitoring programs in the area in recent years, as well as new techniques and well-trained personnel applied to phytoplankton monitoring programs. However, there has been a Red Tide Monitoring Program in Hong Kong since the 1970s, and every single bloom has been recorded in a red tide database which clearly reveals this increasing trend.

Chattonella blooms frequently occur in Japanese waters, but were not recorded in the subtropical waters of South China before 1993. Why have more and more *Chattonella* species and blooms been recorded recently in these waters? Are they exotic species carried in by ballast water, water currents, or other means? We intend to try to find answers to these questions.

Figure 2. Bloom of *Chattonella*

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Lu Songhui and I.J. Hodgkiss, Department of Ecology & Biodiversity, The University of Hong Kong, Pokfulam Road, Hong Kong, Email: Hodgkiss@hkucc.hku.hk

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to morphological adaptation to new environments [16].

To our knowledge, clear identifications of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in the western Mediterranean were restricted to the Strait of Gibraltar and Alboran Sea [8,9] associated with PSP events [9]. Therefore, it can be postulated that the Almeria-Oran front acts as a barrier to the eastward expansion of this species in the Mediterranean.

During a survey aboard R/V "Thalassa" (September 8-30th, 1999) 11 stations were sampled in the Western Mediterranean and Ionian Sea (Fig. 1). Discrete water samples were collected and phytoplankton cells were counted by the Utermöhl method.

Gymnodinium catenatum was observed in the 4 stations from the southern basin of the Western Mediterranean Sea (Alboran Sea, Algerian basin and Sardinia channel; Table 1).

Agitation affects the samples in the Utermöhl chambers. As a consequence the average number of cells per colony in Table 1 is smaller than in the collected living cells due to fracture of the colonies. Despite this, colonies higher than 20 cells were usually

observed. The abundance of *G. catenatum* in the Algerian basin (Sta. 3) was close to the values that caused high PSP toxicity levels in the Alboran Sea [9]. The occurrence along the Algerian basin implies possible expansion towards the Tunisian and Italian coasts or the Balearic Sea according to the circulation patterns of the Modified Atlantic Water in the Western Mediterranean [20].

It seems that harmful algae events are increasing in the Mediterranean Sea [21] and if there are favourable habitats, this allochthonous species could be the

'protagonist of future red tides events.

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Table 1. Abundance (individuals per litre; # l⁻¹) and average colony size.

Station 1			Station 2			Station 3			Station 4		
depth	# l ⁻¹	Ind./col.									
5 m	0		5 m	0		-	-	-	7 m	140*	14*
20 m	1680	4	30 m	310	10	25 m	2050	8	27 m	0	
39 m	680	7	45 m	70	7	55 m	980	9	60 m	0	
59 m	0		70 m	0		80 m	0		90 m	0	

*Only one colony observed.

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Fernando Gómez and Hervé Claustre*,
Laboratoire d'Océanographie de
Villefranche/mer, Observatoire
Océanologique, BP 28, 06234
Villefranche-sur-Mer Cedex, France.
Emails:
fernando.gomez@fitoplancton.com ;
claustre@obs-vlfr.fr;

*To whom post correspondence should
be addressed.

• Argentina

Cyanobacterial blooms in Paso de las Piedras reservoir (Buenos Aires, Argentina)

Paso de las Piedras reservoir, located at south Buenos Aires Province, Argentina, is used for drinking water supply to the cities of Bahía Blanca and Punta Alta, with a population of about 400,000 inhabitants. During April and May, a very noticeable odour was detected associated with a dense algal bloom. The odour, similar to that of an organochloride insecticide, was perceived both in lake-side areas and in the distribution system. Simultaneously, the presence of high contents of particulate material was reported in tap water.

These phenomena provoked the reaction of the users who urged the community authorities and the water supply company for immediate solutions to improve the service. As a result of the demands several studies were undertaken in raw water, in the treatment plants and in the distribution lines. In every case qualitative and quantitative analyses of phytoplankton, physicochemical analyses of water and acute toxicity mouse bioassays were carried out.

Microscopical analyses revealed that two species of Cyanobacteria: *Anabaena circinalis* and *Microcystis aeruginosa* were numerically dominant. The abundance of *Anabaena circinalis* ranged from 48320 to

84032 cells/ml in raw water and from 276 to 2472 cells/ml in tap water.

Acute toxicity bioassays were conducted using water samples taken from tap water, lyophilized and resuspended in physiological solution. Animals used were male mice distributed in two lots: a blank lot, intraperitoneally injected with physiological solution and a sample lot injected with the lyophilized suspension. The result was negative because after the recommended observation period none of the animals injected died and the typical symptoms caused by cyanobacterial hepatotoxins or neurotoxins were not observed. Likewise, no modification of eating behavior or sleep was detected during the experience and the evolution of body weight was similar in both lots.

The strong odour was due to the presence of Geosmin, a metabolite released by *Anabaena circinalis*. Complementary studies revealed the presence of other relevant compounds such as Trihalomethane (x: 70.5 µg/l), Copaene (tricyclo 4.40.02,7 dec-3-ene,1,7-dimethyl-8-(1-methylethyl)-steroisom) (CAS n°: 3856-25-5), by Gas-Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS), Bromocyclohexane (x: 57 µg/l. Very low concentrations of

Xylene (x: 110 ppb), Ethyl benzene (x: 78 ppb) and Toluene (x: 157 ppb) were also detected. The results suggest that Copaene is a precursor of Geosmin and thus it would be very important for the early detection of the odorous compound.

The incident that took place at Paso de las Piedras reservoir in relation to potentially toxic cyanobacteria revealed to the private company and to community authorities involved in water supply service and control, respectively, the need to undertake preventive studies aimed to preserve the quality of water used for human consumption.

Ricardo Echenique, Departamento
Científico Ficología. Fac. Cs. Nat. y
Museo (UNLP), CIC- Provincia de
Buenos Aires, e-mail:
rechen@museo.fcnyml.unlp.edu.ar.

Luis Ferrari, Lab. de Toxicología y
Química Legal, Suprema Corte de
Justicia, Provincia de Buenos Aires.

Diana González, Lab. de Toxicología y
Química Legal. Fac. Qca. Bioqca y
Farmacia (UNSL).

• Argentina

Observations on *Prorocentrum lima* from North- Patagonian coastal waters (Argentina) associated with a human diarrhoeic disease episode

Figure 1. Map indicating the location of the North-Patagonian gulfs.

We carried out a research project on the dynamics of harmful phytoplankton blooms in the North- Patagonian gulfs (Argentina). Recurrent algae blooms of the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium tamarense* have been registered annually since 1980 in the Golfo Nuevo and Golfo San José (Fig. 1) causing human illness and economic losses. The capture and industrialization of shellfish in the region generates 1.0-2.5 million dollars per year provides employment for 150-250 people. The objectives of the project are to determine, through frequent sampling, the population dynamics of *Alexandrium tamarense* and other species known to cause harmful blooms; to study related environmental factors; to search for cysts of dinoflagellates in the bottom sediments; to contribute to the formation of graduate

Figure 2. Microphotograph of *Procerentrum lima* cell in a water sample.

students in taxonomy and ecology of harmful phytoplankton, and to the awareness of human health risks of harmful algal blooms. A major objective of the project is to develop a conceptual model to relate key factors with the onset, magnitude, duration and localization of harmful algal blooms in the North-Patagonian gulfs.

As part of the project, water and shellfish samples are taken every 2 weeks at 3 stations in Golfo Nuevo, Chubut, Argentina (Fig. 1). The stomach contents of at least 5 specimens of the mollusc *Aulacomya atra* ("cholga" or ribbed mussel) are examined under the microscope to identify and estimate the abundance of microalgae, especially noxious one, in the shellfish. *Aulacomya atra* usually feeds on planktonic and benthic microalgae. Last March, approximately 40 persons who ate blue mussels and cholgas at a celebration developed diarrhoeic shellfish poisoning; with diarrhea, nausea and vomiting (the patients were attended at the public hospital in Puerto Madryn). This episode coincided with the presence of the epibenthic *Prorocentrum lima* Ehrenberg (Dodge) (Fig. 2) in the stomach content of *Aulacomya atra* and *Mytilus edulis platensis* and in water samples from Golfo Nuevo and Golfo San José (Chubut Province, Argentina). This species is known

from the area but not previously associated with human illness [1]. Samples of *Aulacomya atra* and *Mytilus edulis platensis* were run on a fluorometric phosphatase assay with positive results, indicating the presence of diarrhoeic toxins in both species (Steve Morton and Lucie Maranda, personal communication)

This brief note aims to alert people to the occurrence of diarrhoeic shellfish poison associated with *Prorocentrum lima* during early autumn in the North Patagonia region. PSP problems associated with *A. tamarense* are usually over by March, and the area is frequently open at that time of the year for shellfish harvesting.

Figure 3. *Aulacomya atra* stomach content showing a cell of *Procerentrum lima*.

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Ana María Gayoso and Néstor Ciocco, Centro Nacional Patagónico. Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas. Boulevard Brown s/n, casilla de correo 128, 9120 Puerto Madryn, Chubut, Argentina, e-mail: gayoso@cenpat.edu.ar.

• Egypt

Toxic red tide species are on rise in Alexandria waters (Egypt)

A monitoring program was carried out in the Eastern Harbour of Alexandria (a relatively, shallow, semi-enclosed basin located in the central part of the city, sheltered from the open Mediterranean Sea by a breakwater of two inlets, area about 2.53 km², average depth 5 m, and a water volume of about 15.2x10⁶ m³, receiving drainage water of 35.2 x10⁶ m³, annually), during the three years 1998 – 2000.

Samples were collected to test the adequacy of short time-scale sampling to fully describe phytoplankton variability and ambient environmental conditions in a dynamic and eutrophic marine basin. The results indicate that red tide blooms (of 24 species, monospecific or in combination) gradually intensified in the neritic waters of Alexandria, and their intensity and geographical extent seem to be on rise; the phenomenon became of regular occurrence in the warm seasons.

At present, the toxic phytoplankton, *Alexandrium catenella*, *Alexandrium ostenfeldii*, *Chattonella antiqua*, and *Gymnodinium mikimotoi*, which are not indigenous in the Eastern Harbour, can be found, representing newly recorded species in Alexandria waters. *C. antiqua* and *G. mikimotoi* appeared suddenly in the harbour during the three year survey, sharing visible phytoplankton bloom periods with different causative species. Inquiries to fishermen and other people from the coastal areas around the harbour, and observation, have revealed that water discoloration was first observed west of Alexandria in Mex Bay (12 Km away from the harbour, a highly eutrophic bay, receiving a daily water input of about 6.6x10⁶ m³, mixed with agro-chemical, industrial and municipal waste waters), about two days earlier than their massive occurrence in the harbour. Thus, these blooms may have been populations that were transferred to the harbour from Mex Bay by local diffusion, since hydrographic processes must be responsible. Yet, the progressive eutrophication in Alexandria waters must share responsibility. Reduced salinity may be partly responsible for the development of *C. antiqua* and *G. mikimotoi*. The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Maximum occurrence of *C. antiqua* and *G. mikimotoi* in the Eastern Harbour of Alexandria from 1998 to 2000.

Species	Peak Day	Cell. l ⁻¹ x10 ⁹	Major Species
<i>Chattonella antiqua</i>	30 Sept. 98	0.54 (7.3%)	<i>Pyramimonas</i> sp. (5.35x10 ⁶ , 73.14%) <i>Cyclotella nana</i> (13.3%)
	27 July 99	0.85 (28%)	<i>Skeletonema costatum</i> (1.5x10 ⁶ , 49.5%) <i>C. nana</i> (12.8%)
	21 May 2000	1.14 (26.64%)	<i>S. costatum</i> (1.37x10 ⁶ , 32%)
	24 Sept.	0.65 (4.96%)	<i>S. costatum</i> (8.43x10 ⁶ , 64.24%)
	7 Oct.	0.31 (5.47%)	<i>S. costatum</i> (2.94x10 ⁶ , 52.41%)
<i>Gymnodinium mikimotoi</i>	14 Sept. 98	0.5 (12.7%)	<i>Leptocylindrus minimum</i> (1.5x10 ⁶ , 38.4%) <i>Cyclotella nana</i> (20.4%) <i>N. longissima</i> (12.7%) <i>S. costatum</i> (11.8%)
	15 Oct. 98	0.13 (9%)	<i>C. nana</i> (0.49x10 ⁶ , 34.8%)
	11 Aug. 99	0.93 (14.65%)	<i>N. longissima</i> (3.7x10 ⁶ , 68%)
	30 May	1.8 (29.6%)	<i>T. nitzschioides</i> (3.87x10 ⁶ , 64.8%)
	9 Oct. 2000	0.42 (10.75%)	<i>L. minimum</i> (2.24x10 ⁶ , 57.5%)

During peak abundance (mixed mainly with diatoms) limited wild fish and faunal mortality was noted, as well as stunned or abnormally swimming fish, providing some evidence of toxicity.

The thermohaline stratification of the water column was a permanent character. *C. antiqua* occurred within a temperature range of 21–26 °C, most frequently between 24.5–26 °C, salinity range 34.5–38.5 psu, mostly 34.5–35 psu. These ranges were close to those for *G. mikimotoi* (22.5–27.2 °C, 34–36.5 psu). In all cases the surface water temperature was > 20°C. Nutrient concentrations were relatively low.

The density of *A. catenella* increased in 2000. The species appeared irregularly from late May to early October, with a peak (10.7x10³ cell l⁻¹) on 23 May (21.5 °C, 35 psu, nitrate 0.8 mM, phosphate 2.3 mM). Also, this peak was recorded within a multi-species bloom of *S. costatum* (26%), *Thalassionema nitzschioides* (17%), *P. minimum* (14.3%), and *Chaetoceros curvesitus* (13%). *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* occurred less frequently than *A. catenella*, but was more abundance. The species in 1998 was seen from mid-September until mid-October, with 14.4x10³ - 18.2x10³ cell l⁻¹ between 27–29 September (24.8–26 °C, 37.5–38 psu, weakly stratified water column and relatively high nutrients), accompanying a

bloom of *Pyramimonas* spp. (2.73x10⁶ cell l⁻¹, 83.8%) on the last day. The survey in 1999 revealed small numbers on 29 May (0.6x10³ cell l⁻¹) and on 4 June (0.5x10³ cell l⁻¹). The species on 11–16 September 2000 reached 14.3 x10³–36.5 x10³ cell l⁻¹, highest on 13 September (26.2 °C, 36.5 psu, Dt 1.2°C, Dpsu 2, nitrate and phosphate of 2.2 mM for each). This peak shared a water discoloration period of with *R. delicatula* (0.84x10⁶ cell l⁻¹, 39.75%), *Thalssiosira* sp. (27.6%) and *S. costatum* (12.8%).

These results suggest that an effective monitoring system should be established urgently, and that predictive techniques should be developed for toxic flagellates and other noxious species in the near-shore and open sea of Alexandria. To this end, it is necessary to examine the ecology of these organisms, particularly in their original sites and in the initial phase of population growth and the relation with the physical mechanisms of dispersion within these embayments. If the initial site of bloom formation of the red tide organisms can be determined, the monitoring of phytoplankton species at this site may allow prediction of red tide outbreaks.

Samia K. Mikhail, National Institute of Oceanography & Fisheries, Kayet Bey, El-Anfoshi, Alexandria, Egypt, E-mail: hany_gamil@yahoo.com.

• Mexico

Unusual HABs in Manzanillo Bay, Colima, Mexico

Figure 1. Geographic situation of the Manzanillo Bay, Colima, Mexico.

In Manzanillo Bay (19°01'–19°07' N, 104°18'–104°26' W, Fig. 1) red tide events are recorded annually at the end of winter and in spring, tides occur in patches and last one or two weeks, and reappear twice or three times in that season according to the oceanographic conditions. In 1999 we observed that some blooms increased in time and space, staying for more than two months and occupying the whole Manzanillo Bay [1]. From weekly monitorings (January to June, 2000), different events, in time and space, were recorded: five phytoplanktonic species and one ciliate were identified to be associated with changes in the color of the marine surface.

At the end of January two red tide patches were dominated by the dinoflagellate *Ceratium furca* and the ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum*, but during February, March and part of April the responsible was *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*, with exception of 11 and 12 March, when *Mesodinium rubrum* was the dominant;

maximum cellular densities were 3258 cel/ml and 7003 cel/ml, respectively. At the end of April two patches were also observed, one due to the silicoflagellate *Dictyocha fibula* and the other due to the diatom *Thalassiothrix sp.*, whereas the last event was recorded in June, with the dinoflagellate *Scrippsiella trochoidea* as the dominant species, with densities of 6486 cel/ml.

Cochlodinium polykrikoides, reported from the first time in spring 1999 in the zone, and subsequently during winter and spring, 2000, develops reddish brown blooms, dense populations and extends widely, which resembles a monoculture. Chains of 8 cells (Fig. 2) and up to 16 cells, with an average of 4 cells, have been found, but no mortality of fishes has been reported [2].

The greatest intensity of these events, in terms of time and extension, occurred when the surface temperature decreased from 25.5°C, at the end of February, and reached to 21.2 °C in the beginning of April; in this period, salinity increased from 34.56 to 34.68

psu, with variations of ± 0.24 .

In comparison with 1999, during 2000 the occurrence of red tides increased notably, and they are related with the lowest temperatures recorded in the area since 1995, condition probably due to the negative anomalies of temperature encountered in the North Pacific Ocean during the period of La Niña [3], as well as the development of internal waves in the area.

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Alejandro Morales-Blake⁽¹⁾, Carolina Cavazos-Guerra. Universidad de Colima, Facultad de Ciencias Marinas, Manzanillo, Colima, México, email: mblake@volcan.ucol.mx.

⁽¹⁾Current address: Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC, Barcelona, Spain, email: almorales@icm.csic.es

David Hernández-Becerril. UNAM, Instituto de Ciencias del Mar y Limnología. México.

Figure 2. *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*. Light microscopy photograph, motile form

CORRIGENDUM

This figure replaces Fig. 1 of the article by Drs Stephen Bates and Don Richard, «Shellfish harvest area closure due to domoic acid - Mill River; Prince Edward Island» which appeared in HAN #21, pp 6-7.

• Ecuador

Red Tides - in Ecuador during La Niña 2000

Large - scale oceanic and atmospheric circulation patterns led to warmer than normal El Niño conditions in the tropical Pacific during 1997-98, followed by nearly normal and cold episode La Niña conditions during 1999-2000.

Consistent cold episode related oceanic features include: below normal sea surface temperatures (SSTs), with negative anomalies greater than - 1° C in the western and central Pacific, and below normal subsurface temperatures in the eastern equatorial Pacific.

Surprisingly few biological data have been published for La Niña years, although outstanding records of high primary production, higher zooplankton biomass and high fish catches were recorded during those years. Red tides have occurred in Ecuadorean waters almost every other year. *Mesodinium rubrum* is the most common causative organism of red tides, related to continual, but less intense upwelling. Blooms can persist for long periods of time, the autotrophic and motility of the organisms making the nutrients of the photo zone and below it available to them. On several occasions red tides of *Gyrodinium instriatum* have been reported in the Gulf of Guayaquil among other organisms (Jiménez, 1993). Large scale red tides were recorded during La Niña, 2000, associated with strong upwelling off the coast of Ecuador.

Along the coast of Ecuador and in the Gulf of Guayaquil, surface temperatures were between 26° and 28° C during February-March, 2000; but below the shallow thermocline at 20 meters depth were between

18° and 20° C. During this period, several large scale algal blooms were recorded along the coast from 4 to 20 March, 2000, and intensive blooms of *Mesodinium rubrum* occurred along the central coast of Ecuador.

Water samples showed a concentration of 3.500 cell/ml of *M. rubrum* with a minor concentration of *Gyrodinium instriatum* of 2.000 cell/ml. The diversity of dinoflagellates was high, mainly due to tropical species of *Ceratium* spp: *C. carriense*, *C. horridum*, *C. tripos* var. *semipulchellum*, *C. fusus*, *C. furca*, *C. trichoceros*, *C. macrocerus*, *C. porrectum*, *C. vultur*, *C. lunula* and *Protopteridinium pentagonum*, *P. oceanium*, *P. brochi*, *P. pellucidum*, *Prorocentrum gracilis*, *Pyrophacus steinii* and minor concentrations of diatoms such as *Coscinodiscus radiatus* and *Proboscia alata*.

On March 30, 2000, an extensive red tide from the northern part of the Gulf of Guayaquil to the southern part of Manabi province was again recorded. The bloom discolored the water and formed long scattered bands extending about 90 miles along the coast and 10 miles wide. The causative species was identified as *Gyrodinium instriatum* with concentrations higher than 10.000 cell/ml. The huge bloom of *G. instriatum* lasted about two weeks. At that time the concentration of *M. rubrum* decreased to 100 cell/ml and a high diversity of dinoflagellate, especially *Ceratium* spp., was again recorded. During the event we observed for the first time in oceanic or coastal waters of Ecuador, chains of *Gymnodinium catenatum*, a toxic

dinoflagellate involved in paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP), although in small concentration about 5- 10 cell/ml.

This organism is now isolated and maintained in culture. Preliminary findings by bioassay suggests that *G. catenatum* accounts for toxicity. These findings highlight the need for close monitoring of the coastal waters of Ecuador where important shrimp and fish culture facilities are located.

In mid-April blooms of *Ceratium trichoceros* and *Ceratium macrocerus* were recorded along with a high diversity of dinoflagellates. From May to July, 2000, SSTs were lower in the Gulf of Guayaquil and along the coast of Ecuador, from 18° to 19° C. In July a new red tide of *M. rubrum* was observed and low concentrations of *G. catenatum* was still present.

Until November, 2000, no further red tide were reported along the coast of Ecuador, although the cold conditions of La Niña persisted in the tropical Pacific and off the coast of Ecuador until the end of the year.

During these successive red tides, no mortalities of marine fauna was detected.

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IOC Manuals and Guides No. 41

Potentially Harmful Microalgae in the Western Indian Ocean Microalgues Potentiellement Nuisibles d'Ouest de l'Océan Indien

By Gert Hansen, Jean Turquet, Jean Pascal Quod, Loïc Ten-Hage, Charles Lugomela, Margereth Kyewalyanga, Mira Hurbungs, Peter Waiye, Bernard

Ogongo, Shandrack Tunje & Henri Rakotoarinjanahary

This publication is a result of a cooperative research project, WIOHAB, which was implemented between 1998 and 2000 by the Kenya Marine and Fisheries Research Institute (Mombasa), Institute of Marine Science, (Zanzibar), Albion Fisheries Research Centre (Mauritius), National Centre for Oceanographic Research (Madagascar), Agence pour la Recherche et la Valorisation Marines (Reunion Island), and the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at the University of

Copenhagen (Denmark). Up to now, there have been no comprehensive publications on harmful algae in the Western Indian Ocean.

The project was implemented within the framework of the IOC Sub-commission for the Western Indian Ocean, IOCINCWIO, and was funded through the IOC by Sweden (SAREC) and Denmark (DANIDA).

The guide is bilingual, English-French. Available from October 2001.

Copies can be ordered at: p.boned@unesco.org; fax + 33 45685812; and: IOC of UNESCO, 1 rue Miollis, 75732 Paris cedex 15, Paris, France, attn. P. Boned.

Announcing a New Journal: Harmful Algae

Editors-In-Chief

Sandra E. Shumway, Natural Science Division, Southampton College, Long Island University, Southampton, NY 11968, USA
Email: sshumway@southampton.liunet.edu

Theodore Smayda, Graduate School of Oceanography, University of Rhode Island, Kingston, RI 02881, USA
Email: tsmayda@gso.uri.edu

Associate Editors

Geoffrey E. Codd, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Dundee, Dundee DD1 4HN, Scotland, UK
Email: g.a.codd@dundee.ac.uk

Jeffrey L.C. Wright, UNCW Center for Marine Science, One Marvin Moss Lane, Wilmington, NC 28409, USA
Email: wrightj@uncwil.edu

Adriana Zingone, Stazione Zoologica 'A. Dohrn', Villa Comunale, I-80121 Naples, Italy, Email: zingone@alpha.szn.it

This new journal aims at providing a forum to promote knowledge of harmful microalgae, including cyanobacteria, as well as monitoring, management and control of these organisms. Both original research and review papers will be considered.

Papers dealing with the following aspects of harmful microalgae and cyanobacteria in marine and fresh waters will be considered:

- the distribution, life histories and taxonomy of harmful microalgae;
- the physiology and toxicology of harmful microalgae;
- harmful microalgal bloom ecology;
- trophic, socio-economic, public health and aquacultural impacts of harmful microalgal bloom events;
- occurrence, methods of detection and chemical structure of toxins in harmful microalgae, cyanobacteria, foodwebs and seafood;
- factors controlling toxin production, biosynthesis and chemical ecology.

Note: Papers dealing with pharmacology fall outside of the scope of the journal.

All papers will be subject to peer review. Authors will receive proofs. The editors, referees, and publisher will make every effort to expedite publication, the co-operation of authors in this task is welcomed.

Initially the journal is planned to appear quarterly, the first issue is expected to appear early 2002.

Authors of papers published in the first volume of *Harmful Algae* will receive a one-year subscription to the journal.

Visit the *Harmful Algae* website for full information on this new journal: www.elsevier.com/locate/hal

New image database of HAB species on the Web

A consortium of engineers and marine scientists have developed a software tool for automatically labelling HAB species (European contract MAS3-ct98-0188). Classification is based on a specimen's contour as is the case of *Dinophysis* species. The team developed a software called "Dinoflagellate Categorisation by Artificial Neural Network" (DiCANN). DiCANN can be trained to recognise patterns of the problem dinoflagellates in a given locality provided it is trained with a minimum of 40 pictures of each species. It uses six analysis channels in this process, which are area, shape, local Fourier contrast, texture, texture density and internal junction structure. Performance has been shown to be proportional to morphological variance of the species. In previous work a version of the software was demonstrated to achieve 85% accuracy on 23 species of dinoflagellate (MEPS 139:281-287, 1996). Because DiCANN is trainable, it does not require the calibration normally required by image analysis software.

During the project over 1000 digital images were archived on the consortium's

Light microscopy observations of a) *D. acuminata*; b) *D. sacculus* from Galician Rías. Scale bars = 10 μ m

distributed web database. The species are *Dinophysis acuta*, *D. acuminata*, *D. caudata*, *D. rotundata*, *D. tripos*, *D. fortii*, *D. sacculus* and the small forms of these species. These are now available to the scientific community at <http://www.dist.unige.it/dicann>.

The database is searchable, all images are in bmp format and can be downloaded.

The consortium also have available a database in excess of 5000 images of over 23 species of dinoflagellates from the Eastern North Atlantic Ocean (see <http://newlyn.cis.plym.ac.uk/dicann> for details). These images are in jpeg format.

The consortium's publications are also available at this web site, including: Dinoflagellate categorisation by artificial neural network (DiCANN) in: Hallegraeff, Blackburn, Bolch and Lewis Harmful Algal Blooms, IOC of UNESCO (in press), Proceedings of the 9th Int. Conf. on HABs Tasmania, February 2000.

Phil Culverhouse, Centre for Intelligent Systems, DCEE, University of Plymouth, UK. PL4 8AA, Co-ordinator DiCANN (European contract Mas3-ct98-0188), Email: pculverhouse@plymouth.ac.uk

• Mexico

First North-American and Caribbean Training Course on Marine Toxins and Harmful Algal Blooms

After years of planning and expectancy raised during the last five years, the *IOC-CIBNOR First North-American and Caribbean Training Course on Marine Toxins and Harmful Algal Blooms* was held at the Centro de Investigaciones Biológicas del Noroeste, S.C. (CIBNOR), Mexico from 24 November to 10 December, 2000. The course was jointly sponsored by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, CIBNOR, Mexico, as well as by other institutions and private companies.

The course was organized by Arturo P. Sierra-Beltran (CIBNOR, Mexico) and Roberto Cortés Altamirano (National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico), with the support of the IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, and hosted by the Postgraduate Studies Programme, CIBNOR (Mexico).

Yasuwo Fukuyo (University of Tokyo, Japan), Isabel Bravo (Spanish Institute of Oceanography, Vigo, Spain), José M. Franco (IIM-CSIC, Vigo, Spain), Sergio Licea Duran (National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico), Casimiro Ramirez Camarena (National Fisheries Institute, Mexico), Berta Olivia Arredondo Vega, Ma. Lourdes Morquecho, Daniel Bernardo Lluch Cota, Salvador Emilio Lluch Cota, and Jose Bustillos Guzmán (CIBNOR, México) were invited to give lectures. The 8 participants came from 6 countries: CHILE, COLOMBIA, COSTA RICA, GUATEMALA, TRINIDAD & TOBAGO and MEXICO.

The objective of the course was to disseminate basic knowledge on toxic phytoplankton, including the taxonomy and distribution of harmful algae, the determination of phycotoxins, and the development of monitoring programs. It was a theoretical and practical training course.

Lectures and seminars on the general aspects of the HAB problem initiated the activities (two working days), followed by specific subjects: climatology and oceanography, taxonomy and biogeography, toxin action and determination, remote sensors, public health, resource protection and monitoring programs among others (12 working days).

Participants were trained on practical taxonomy of phytoplankton including

diatoms and cyanobacteria by the use of light microscopy. Dinoflagellate and cyst collection, isolation, concentration, cleaning, culturing and cloning, and cyst germination were subjects also covered with theoretical and practical lectures, as well. Accordingly with the variety of toxins present in the area, different methods for detection of toxins were carried out by the participants or demonstrated: mouse bioassays, ELISA tests and HPLC. Pigments analysis by HPLC and fatty acids determination by MS-GC were also performed by the participants.

The activities were directed to scientists of medium and high level that have working knowledge of the harmful marine algae and/or toxins, and are presently or in the near future will be involved on monitoring programs for research or protection purposes. The opportunity to CIBNOR of serving as a mean to pass the experience of a numerous group of experts towards the Caribbean and Central American countries, including as well some in South America, is more important than ever, if we look for a well integrated global economy and social development.

The gathering of experts to discuss special issues on the topic of HAB was stressed for establishing the similarities and differences between distinct geographical regions. The discussions held during the course will help to improve the skills of the participants (including the lecturers) in taxonomy, biogeography, toxin chemistry and toxicology, and will enable them to implement (or improve) reliable research and monitoring programs related to harmful algal events at the coastlines of their respective countries.

A series of books, manuals and materials were provided as teaching aids. Among them, highlights the effort of Dr. Y. Fukuyo who negotiated the fast publication by ANESC, Tokyo University, of the Technical Guide for Modern Dinoflagellate Cyst Study (Guia Técnica para el Estudio de Quistes de Dinoflagelados Actuales) and also to Dr. Beatriz Reguera from the Oceanographic Center in Vigo (COI-IEO), who, in a very tight time schedule, translated the Spanish version on time to be distributed during the course. Each participant was

provided with a take-home training course guide, summarizing the state of the art (according to the lecturers) of the harmful microalgae taxonomy and identification, toxin chemistry, ecophysiology and culturing. This training course guide is the core work for the elaboration of an improved Spanish version of the IOC Manual on Harmful Algae (currently under editing process), which we hope will see the light during 2001.

Each participant received a copy of interactive CDs to be used as an aid on the study of Harmful Marine Algae: 1) Atlas of Dinoflagellates v.1.5 & HAB Related Photograph Sets v.1.0, 2) Diatoms from the South China Sea 3) Colección de Información Ambiental para el Pacífico Mexicano and 4-7) Application of Satellite Remote Sensing on the Detection of Algal Blooms.

There were more than two weeks of very long working sessions but it worth it. We end up with a bunch of friends along the Americas and also new partners on the ANCA Project. At the moment, we will wait for feedback to evaluate the possibilities of continuity of training activities alike on the IOCARIBE region.

Arturo Sierra Beltrán, Biotoxins Laboratory, CIBNOR, Currently: Molecular Genetics Laboratory, CIBNOR, Fax: 52(112)5 36 25, Email: asierra@cibnor.mx

Roberto Cortés Altamirano, Plankton Lab. Mazatlán, (ICMyL-UNAM), Fax: 52(69)82 61 33, Email: roberto@mar.icmyl.unam.mx

• Tunisia

On the presence of potentially toxic algae in the lagoons of Tunisia

Since 1995, a national monitoring programme has been in operation in the areas of bivalve mollusc production in Tunisia (Gulf of Gabès, Boughrara Sea, Lake Tunis and Lake Bizerte), with the objective of microbiological control of live bivalve molluscs and the detection of potentially toxic microalgae in order to evaluate the toxicity.

The Tunisian lagoons (Fig. 1) have been subject to several research studies since the dystrophy crises in the autumn period. Guelorget (1992) reports the presence of the toxic species *Gymnodinium nagasakiense* in the Boughrara Sea with a concentration of 8×10^5 cells/L during severe mortalities in aquaculture operations in Southern Tunisia (AST). Romdhane et al (1998) explains the mortalities of fish in the lagoons of Boughrara and Ghar El Melh as due to toxicity of blooms of *Gymnodinium aureolum* and *Alexandrium minutum* respectively. The maximum concentrations reached 5.3×10^5 (August 1991) and 2×10^5 cells/L (June 1996), respectively. Furthermore, according to Arzul (1998), the haemolytic activity of *Gymnodinium cf nagasakiense* (sample from Gulf of Gabès) diminishes if anoxia or oxygen supersaturation occurs.

During the period from September 1996 to September 1999, we did not record mortalities of fish in Lake Bizerte or in the lake north of Tunis although increased concentrations of dinoflagellates were found. There were blooms of *Gymnodinium nagasakiense* in December 1996 (1.27×10^6 cell/L) and *Protoperidinium quinquecorne* in August 1999 (14.5×10^6 cells/L) which caused restricted areas of red water. In Lake Tunis (northern part) and in Tunis Channel, blooms recorded during the autumn were due to *Gyrodinium impudicum* with concentrations from 1.02×10^5 to 1.73×10^6 cells/L.

With respect to other potentially toxic microalgae, concentrations of *Dinophysis* varied from 0 to 1280 cells/L and rarely exceeded concentrations above 500 cells/L in Lake Tunis (northern part). The dominant species *D. sacculus* was accompanied by *D. caudata*, *D. acuminata* and *D. fortii*. These occurred primarily during October and November, and secondarily during May

and June. In Tunis Channel, we found the same species and the lowest *Dinophysis* concentrations. Furthermore, we noted the presence of *Pseudonitzschia spp* in June 1998, at densities at 4.6×10^6 cells/L.

In Bizerte Lagoon, concentrations of *Dinophysis spp* reached values in the order of 2.6×10^4 cells/L in May 1999. The dominant species were *D. sacculus* and *D. caudata*, which appeared in December. We also detected the presence of *Ostreopsis siamensis* in Lake Bizerte and Tunis Channel at concentrations of 250 and 100 cells/L respectively.

In addition to the phytoplankton analyses, we carried out sampling of phanerogames (*Cymodocea nodosa*) and found *Prorocentrum lima* at a density at 3362 cells/100 grams of wet weight in a sample from Lake Tunis (northern part). Lawrence et al (1998) have shown that *P. lima* is an epiphyte on macroalgae like *Pilayella littoralis* and is often responsible for the production of DSP toxins and toxicity of mussels in Nova Scotia (Canada). In the Ghar El Melh lagoon, increased levels of *Prorocentrum lima* was recorded (densities above 1.5×10^4 cells/L, December 1996). Turki and El Abed (1999) have also reported the sporadic presence of *P. lima* in Lake Bizerte and in Tunis Channel. The *Prorocentrum* species found in Tunisian coastal waters are: *P. micans*, *P. gracilis*, *P. triestinum*, *P. minimum*, *P. concavum*, *P. mexicanum*, *P. compressum* and *P. belizeanum*. The first three species, and in particular *P. triestinum* are very abundant in Lake Tunis and Lake Bizerte.

The coastal lagoons and lakes represent in general a zone of high productivity. It can be concluded that these fragile ecosystems are subject to anthropogenic disturbance. In fact, the presence of algal blooms and the dominance of dinoflagellates as compared to diatoms characterises a degradation of the biological quality of the water. Furthermore, the periodic dystrophy events in the different lagoons are quite surely linked to the phenomena of anoxia, and causes high turbidity of the water due to large amounts of organic matter.

Map of Tunisia, lagoons location.

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In Memoriam: Estela de Sousa e Silva (1921-2000)

Dr. Estela de Sousa e Silva was born on the 21 August 1921 in Lisbon where she died on the 6 September 2000.

E. Sousa Silva obtained her degree in Biology in 1943 at the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon. After a three years period of teaching she became interested in phytoplankton and developed several research studies as an investigator at “Junta de Investigação do Ultramar” and later at “Instituto de Biologia Marinha” where she stayed until 1971. She developed her scientific career at these Institutes, and also spent periods abroad with famous masters such as Trygve Braarud.

She made detailed studies on the marine microplankton, dinoflagellates, diatoms, and also Tintinoidea present in Portuguese coastal waters, and also in Angola, Moçambique, and Dakar, this last region through the interest of the “Institut Français d’Afrique Noire”.

As a consequence of the occurrence of severe poisoning episodes with paralytic symptoms after consumption of shellfish from Obidos Lagoon (80km north Lisbon) in 1946 and 1955, she was asked to study phytoplankton communities in this lagoon. She identified several dense populations of dinoflagellates associated with biotoxicity. By the 50’s, the microplankton in Obidos lagoon had become her main research interest. She implemented unialgal culturing for the dinoflagellates isolated from Portuguese marine waters, as a means of species identification and cytological and toxicological research.

In view of the health implications related to toxic dinoflagellate blooms, Dr. Estela de

Sousa e Silva continued her career at the “Instituto Nacional de Saúde” and directed the Laboratory of Experimental Microbiology (LME), where she remained from 1971 until her retirement in 1991

E. Sousa Silva made several contributions to the science of harmful algal, promoting cytological and ultrastructural studies aimed at understanding the origin of dinoflagellate toxicity. She was also involved in the implementation of the shellfish toxicity monitoring programme along the Portuguese coasts. She found intracellular bacteria in some dinoflagellates, and initiated several research lines related to toxicity based on the ultrastructural relationships between these microorganisms and the role of bacteria in toxins production. Simultaneously she studied the growth, cytology and nuclear cycle of dinoflagellates and assessed the role of small cells observed in dense populations both in clonal cultures and in natural bloom population in their life history.

She published a considerable number of articles from 1948 to 1995 during her long and fruitful career. Her research on dinoflagellate biology and HAB is being continued and the algal culture she initiated is maintained as the “LME E. Sousa Silva algal culture collection”. It is being expanded with cyanobacterial clones isolated from Portuguese freshwater reservoirs.

A brief list of some of the more significant publications of Estela de Sousa e Silva follows:

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Announcing the II International Conference on Harmful Algae Management and Mitigation

Qingdao, China 12-16 November, 2001

Harmful algae and their toxins can have serious impacts on health, prosperity and commerce. These impacts include contamination of seafood, damage to aquaculture and fisheries, direct human exposure (dermal, aerosol, ingestion), and aesthetic degradation. Furthermore, concern over the presence of algal toxins in seafood, or the proliferation of harmful algae, can lead to impediments to otherwise fruitful international trade.

The First International Conference on Harmful Algae Management and Mitigation was held in the Philippine Islands in May, 1999. Continuing the work begun there, this second conference will review the nature of harmful algae and their impacts, and then explore options for their management and mitigation.

The goal of the HAMM conferences is to develop practical strategies for minimizing the impacts of harmful algae and their toxins on human well-being and commerce,

throughout and beyond the Asia-Pacific region.

For information please visit the HAMM conference web page at: <http://vm.cfsan.fda.gov/~frf/sfhamm.html> or contact:

Sherwood Hall, Ph.D., FDA, HFS-426, 200 C Street SW, Washington, DC 20204, phone: 1 202 205 4818, fax: 1 202 205 4881, Email: shall@cfsan.fda.gov and spindrift@erols.com

Future events

JUNE 2002

4th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MOLLUSCAN SHELLFISH SAFETY.

The web site of the 4th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety has been updated with the second announcement. Call for contributions and information on travel and accommodation, registration, and instructions for abstract preparation is included.

Web site: <http://www.atlanticocongresos.com/moluscos/index.html>

The topics of the conference will include:

- Microbiological contamination
- Chemical contamination and bioaccumulation
- Harmful and toxic algal events
- Shellfish contamination by marine biotoxins
- Depuration
- Management and mitigation
- Water quality at harvesting sites
- Public health, epidemiology and toxicology
- Monitoring, quality assurance programmes and regulatory controls
- Allergies associated with shellfish consumption

Help to divulge this information would be deeply appreciated.

Conference secretariat address:

ICMSS/Antonio Villalba, Centro de Investigaci3n Mariñas, Apdo. 13, 36620 Vilanova de Arousa, Pontevedra, Spain. Phone: 34 986500155, Fax: 34 986506788, Email: icmss@cimacoron.org

OCTOBER 2002

TENTH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HARMFUL ALGAE, October 21-25 2002, St. Pete Beach, Florida, USA. Convener: Karen Steidinger. Further intomation at: <http://www.state.fl.us/fwc/redtide/>

GEOHAB

Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms

A Programme of International Co-operative Research on HABS in Marine and Brackish Waters

GEOHAB Mission:

Foster international co-operative research on HABS in ecosystem types sharing common features, comparing the key species involved and the oceanographic processes that influence their population dynamics.

For further information and copies of the GEOHAB Science Plan visit the web at: <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab>,

or contact the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen (see below)

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

Compiled and edited by Tim Wyatt, Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas, CSIC, Eduardo Cabello 6, 36208 Vigo, Spain; Tel.: +34 986 23 19 30/23 19 73; Fax: +34 986 29 27 62; E-mail: twyatt@nautilus.iim.csic.es and M3nica Lion, Centro Científico y de Comunicaci3n sobre Algas Nocivas COI-IEO, Apdo. 1552, 36200 Vigo, Spain; Tel.: +34 986 49 21 11; Fax: +34 986 49 20 03; E-mail: monica.lion@vi.ieo.es

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*Project Coordinator: Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae University of Copenhagen, Botanical Institute, Øster Farimagsgade 2D, DK-1353 Copenhagen K, Denmark
Tel.: +45 33 13 44 46, Fax.: +45 33 13 44 47
E-mail: hab@bot.ku.dk
Production Editor: Botanical Institute, Copenhagen*